

ONLINE RESUME BUILDER FOR JOB

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Abstract. The Online Resume Builder flow is an automated solution designed to streamline the process of creating and downloading resumes in PDF format. It efficiently manages every step involved in building a resume, ensuring a smooth and intuitive experience. The system offers flexible and convenient features, allowing users to quickly craft professional resumes with minimal effort. With customizable templates and clear formatting, users can easily input personal details, work experience, education, and skills. The builder allows real-time editing, saving, and downloading, making it convenient for frequent updates. It also supports multi-language inputs, providing a versatile tool for job seekers across different regions and industries.

Keyword: resume templates, Professional resume, experience, education, skills, PDF resume download

INTRODUCTION

In the current digital environment, companies want effective techniques that increase convenience, reliability, and data security. The use of digital tools by human beings increases in popularity as technologies develop. Another good sample of this progress is the Resume Builder Website, providing a fast and energy-efficient technique for creating unique resumes. This website makes the job of creating resumes on paper simpler and more efficient. Users may develop, update, and maintain their resumes comfortably due to helpful functions involving real-time editing, an extensive choice of template suggestions, and easy-to-use user interfaces. In a hurry resume future generations. Customers can reduce time by writing and formatting their resumes in only a few clicks, allowing them to look amazing. The resume-creating tool also helps users in structuring their data correctly so they may better display their skills and experience.

PROBLEM

This system is a window application that makes users create and modify professional-looking resumes fast. It can be used client-side or server-side. It improves database inserting and updating methods, decreasing wait times, and increasing resume skills. The Laravel framework and MySQL Workbench Server are both used by the PHP-written system. The goal of the resume-building website is to give users an effortless procedure beginning with registration and ending with the completion of the resume [1]. Users need to sign up if they

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want to create a profile, where they may enter personal details and career goals. Using the platform's selection of customizable styles and sections for skills, work experience, education, projects, and languages, users may tailor their resumes to various job applications.

APPROACH

This system consists of two roles. There are administrator and user within a template creation and management system. Users begin by logging in with their email and password. If the credentials are correct, they proceed to create a template by filling in required information, selecting a design, and customizing it before downloading the final template as a PDF. Once the template is complete, users conclude their session by logging out.

Administrators follow a similar login process, after which they gain access to various system management tasks. These tasks include viewing charts that display weekly and monthly registration data, searching for information about admins and users, and managing lists of both. After performing these tasks, administrators log out, ending their session. The flowchart effectively outlines the key steps for both users and administrators, highlighting the system's functionality and the distinct roles within it.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

After the system is developed, it must undergo comprehensive testing to ensure it operates without bugs or errors. During this phase, any issues identified need to be promptly addressed by the developer to maintain the system's functionality. Testing is a critical process that involves evaluating the software to identify discrepancies between the actual output and the expected results, helping to ensure the system meets its requirements. This phase serves as both a validation and verification process, crucial for assessing the overall quality of the system. System testing is not solely the responsibility of the development team; it also requires collaboration with external stakeholders to validate that the system meets their expectations and requirements [3]. This collaborative approach ensures that the system is thoroughly vetted for user acceptance before deployment.

RESULTS

After initial installation, users may quickly and easily create and update their resumes by applying the platform's easy-to-use editing tool. To provide them with an updated design, they may quickly determine their resumes and make changes to the design, content, and style. Job recruiters can easily receive completed resumes from users, given the platform's ability to convert resumes into PDF format. The Resume Builder website provides an important advance in resume manufacturing technology. This gives users a choice of powerful tools and personalized features that increase performance and presentation quality, helping them fill the difference between creating a traditional resume and today's digital efficiency. By correctly displaying their experiences, skill sets, and goals in the future, users of this platform will

increase their chances of success in today's highly skilled job market. Figure3 illustrates the implementation process of the Online Resume Builder, providing a visual representation of how the system is developed, tested, and prepared for final use [2].

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

In today's digital age, technology has revolutionized how we handle tasks, making processes more efficient and accessible. Traditional methods, such as manually creating resumes, are now being replaced by online resume builders that simplify and enhance the process. This project aims to develop an online resume builder that streamlines the creation of professional resumes. Many job seekers struggle with creating resumes manually, often finding it time-consuming and challenging. Our online tool will provide users with a user-friendly interface that simplifies resume creation, offering easy-to-use templates and customization options. It will enable quick data entry, intuitive design adjustments, and easy formatting, resulting in polished and professional resumes. The online resume builder will improve the efficiency and accuracy of resume creation, ensuring that users can produce high-quality resumes with ease. By leveraging this tool, individuals can create standout resumes effortlessly, boosting their chances of making a strong impression in the job market.

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